

DIFFERENTIAL ANALYSIS OF LONELINESS AND PERSONAL POTENTIAL AMONG UNIVERSITY STUDENTS

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Abstract. In recent years, the phenomenon of loneliness has attracted psychological scientists as one of the pressing problems of our modern society. Statistics show that during the pandemic, the tendency to loneliness increased in young people compared to older people. The problem of loneliness is widely studied in foreign psychology, where it is studied on the basis of various theories, concepts, approaches, positions, directions. This article presents the results of our research on the mechanisms of perception of loneliness and the impact of this phenomenon on the personal potential of students in Uzbekistan. As the personal potential of a person characterizes the inner physical and spiritual energy of a person, his active position aimed at creative self-expression and self-realization. The degree of statistical reliability of the results obtained was confirmed by methods of mathematical statistics: the Mann-Whitney criterion, as well as the Spearman correlation coefficient.

Keywords: personal potential, loneliness, self-realization, anxiety, creative self-expression, physical energy, spiritual energy, differential analysis, scale of general loneliness experience, scale of dependence on communication, scale of positive loneliness

Introduction

In scientific research conducted around the world, considerable attention is being paid to issues related to the preservation of human mental health, particularly those associated with the characteristics of loneliness manifested through emotional experiences. These studies also emphasize the necessity of investigating such issues as determining the priorities of the higher education system in educating individuals in accordance with the principles of social and psychological development, as well as improving the quality of training highly qualified specialists equipped with modern knowledge and strong personal potential. Personal potential refers to the

qualities of individuals that fundamentally influence the outcomes of the activities in which they are engaged across various fields of endeavor.

In recent years, important tasks have been identified in our republic aimed at the legal and regulatory consolidation of requirements for studying youth psychology and establishing the foundations for their implementation. These include: “training highly qualified, creatively thinking specialists capable of making independent decisions based on international standards, demonstrating their intellectual abilities, and developing as spiritually enlightened individuals...” [1], as well as “educating spiritually and intellectually developed youth who possess serious views toward life situations” [3]. The practical implementation of these tasks creates the need to search for new theoretical solutions aimed at deepening scientific research into the psycho-emotional states of students that hinder their psychological and intellectual growth.

According to M. S. Kagan [2], five potentials can be distinguished within the structure of personality:

1. The gnoseological potential of personality. It is characterized by the volume and quality of information possessed by an individual. It includes knowledge about the external world, nature, society, and self-awareness, and depends on a person’s innate intellect, education, and experience.
2. The axiological potential of personality. It is determined by the system of value orientations acquired during the process of socialization – ideals, life goals, beliefs, and aspirations — as a unity of personal consciousness and self-consciousness.
3. The creative potential of personality. It is characterized by acquired and independently developed skills and abilities related to action and work, whether constructive or destructive, productive or reproductive, as well as the degree of their realization in a particular sphere of activity.
4. The communicative potential of personality. It is determined by the extent and forms of sociability, the nature and stability of interpersonal contacts, the content of interpersonal communication, and is expressed through social roles.
5. The artistic potential of personality. It is determined by the content and intensity of artistic needs and the ways in which these needs are satisfied.

The degree of personal potential may be influenced by the feeling of loneliness, as loneliness can manifest itself in both positive and negative forms. In its negative manifestation, loneliness is associated with conditions such as depression, anxiety,

a tendency toward interpersonal conflicts, the use of psychoactive substances and alcohol abuse, as well as suicidal tendencies. Therefore, this study attempts to conduct a differential analysis of students' feelings of loneliness and determine the extent to which this phenomenon affects their personal potential.

Materials and Methods

Interpretations of approaches within the historical development of world psychology concerning loneliness as an objectively existing phenomenon, including its nature, development, and manifestations, have been sufficiently reflected in scientific sources. Psychodynamic, cognitive, systemic, interactionist, phenomenological, humanistic, biological, and existential approaches to the study of loneliness differ from one another in their profound investigation and theoretical analysis of the problem [5]. The scientific study of the feeling of loneliness is distinguished by both its complexity and productivity. Therefore, investigating its emergence requires an important methodologically grounded stage of research into external and internal causes, their situational dependence, and the influence of social changes occurring within society.

General aspects of loneliness as a socio-psychological phenomenon have been studied by prominent psychologists such as K. A. Abulkhanova-Slavskaya, S. G. Korchagina, L. I. Starovoitova, G. M. Tikhonov, S. G. Trubnikova, Zh. V. Puzanova, N. E. Pokrovsky, S. A. Vetrov, Yu. M. Shvalb, O. V. Dancheva, I. S. Kon, O. B. Dolginova, E. V. Filindash, and A. U. Kharash. Their studies examined the cultural-historical forms and psychological characteristics of loneliness during adolescence and youth [6].

In our republic, comparatively little attention has been devoted to the study of students' feelings of loneliness in specific scientific investigations. In particular, the studies conducted by V. M. Karimova on the role of interpersonal communication in personality development analyzed issues such as how loneliness and lack of communication lead individuals to experience emotional instability, heightened emotional excitability, self-doubt, fear, anxiety, and psychological distress. Research conducted by G. V. Shoumarov, N. A. Soginov, U. D. Kodirov, B. M. Umarov, G. K. Tulaganova, and G. B. Suleymanova was primarily aimed at studying psychological characteristics during childhood and adolescence, with particular emphasis on the influence of loneliness on the emergence of deviant behavior, character accentuation, suicide, self-esteem, and self-control problems [4; 6].

Nevertheless, by the twenty-first century, the phenomenon of loneliness among

students and the problem of personal potential had not yet become the subject of specialized research in Uzbekistan. During the course of our study, the “Differential Questionnaire of the Experience of Loneliness” developed by E. N. Osin and D. A. Leontiev was employed. The study involved 120 students from the Faculty of Pedagogy and Psychology at Fergana State University.

Research Results

The question of determining which statistical criterion should be applied to analyze students’ performance according to the methodology led to testing whether the respondents’ results corresponded to a normal distribution.

Table 1

Results of testing the conformity of the data obtained through the “Differential Questionnaire of the Experience of Loneliness”

Scales	Min	Max	Mean	Std. d.	z	p
General Loneliness	15,00	46,00	25,30	6,245	2,783	0,000
Dependence on Communication	24,00	54,00	37,44	6,91	1,873	0,002
Positive Loneliness	16,00	37,00	28,11	5,28	2,676	0,000

Note: *** $p < 0.001$

It was established that the results obtained on the scales “General Loneliness” ($Z = 2.783$; $p < 0.001$), “Dependence on Communication” ($Z = 24.00$; $p < 0.001$), and “Positive Loneliness” ($Z = 2.676$; $p < 0.001$) did not correspond to the law of normal distribution. Based on these findings, at the subsequent stages of the study, the scales of the “Differential Questionnaire of the Experience of Loneliness” were analyzed using nonparametric criteria. For this purpose, statistical analysis of the results was conducted using the Mann–Whitney U test, while correlation analysis was performed using Spearman’s rank correlation coefficient.

Table 2

Correlation of the scales of the “Differential Questionnaire of the Experience of Loneliness”

Scales	General Loneliness	Dependence on Communication	Positive Loneliness

		1 st year	3 rd year		1 st year	3 rd year		1 st year	3 rd year
General Loneliness	1	1	1	-0,128**	-0,175*	-0,147*	0,262**	0,109	0,264**
Dependence on Communication			1		1	1	-0,226**	-0,155*	-0,401**
Positive Loneliness							1	1	1

Note: * $p < 0,05$; ** $p < 0,01$

Dependence on communication demonstrates a negative correlation with the scale of positive loneliness ($r = -0.226$; $p < 0.01$). The findings indicate that, due to students' increasing desire to avoid loneliness, they develop a painful and unpleasant attitude toward it. As a result, they are unable to experience positive emotions associated with loneliness and fail to identify constructive ways of coping with it. A negative correlation between the scales of general loneliness and dependence on communication among first-year students ($r = -0.175$; $p < 0.05$) suggests that feelings of isolation from others, limited ability to communicate effectively, and experiences of loneliness contribute to reduced tolerance toward lonely individuals and situations. Furthermore, the negative correlation between the scales of dependence on communication and positive loneliness ($r = -0.155$; $p < 0.05$) among first-year students indicates their inability to experience positive emotions related to loneliness or recognize its constructive potential, as they tend to avoid situations of solitude and perceive loneliness as an unpleasant and painful experience.

Among third-year students, the scales of general loneliness and dependence on communication also demonstrated a negative correlation ($r = -0.148$; $p < 0.05$). According to the results, an increased tendency toward general loneliness among students reduces their sense of dependence on communication. The absence of warm interpersonal relationships, difficulties in establishing contact with others, and an intensified sense of loneliness contribute to indifference toward communication. In addition, an increase in the general feeling of loneliness is associated with an increase in positive loneliness ($r = 0.264$; $p < 0.01$). The lack of close interpersonal relationships and the inability to establish emotional closeness with others indicate that, under conditions of isolation and detachment from their social environment, students begin to use solitude for positive purposes. The scales of dependence on

communication and positive loneliness among third-year students also demonstrated a negative correlation ($r = -0.401$; $p < 0.01$). This suggests that students who exhibit a stronger dependence on communication are less likely to perceive loneliness as a positive experience.

Conclusion

Based on the results of the empirical study, the following conclusions were drawn:

First, first-year students perceive loneliness as an unpleasant and painful experience. Consequently, they are unable to experience positive emotions associated with solitude and fail to identify constructive solutions to the problem of loneliness. This negatively affects the personal potential of first-year students.

Second, third-year students demonstrate a greater tendency toward general feelings of loneliness. However, an increase in general loneliness among them is accompanied by an increase in positive loneliness. This may be explained by the experience they have acquired during their years of study. By finding positive aspects in solitude, third-year students are able to preserve their inner physical and spiritual energy, maintain effectiveness in academic activities, and direct themselves toward creative self-expression and self-realization. This indicates the positive influence of loneliness on the personal potential of third-year students.

Third, the presence of painful attitudes toward loneliness among first-year students necessitates the effective implementation of modern psychotherapeutic and psychocorrective interventions.

Based on the empirical findings obtained in the study, the following recommendations were developed for students:

1. It is important to emphasize that students should learn to live in the present while developing an understanding of the system of personal potentials.
2. Students should be taught to distinguish between positive and negative forms of loneliness. Particular attention should be devoted to the effective use of positive loneliness.
3. It is necessary to help students clarify their life goals, as this strengthens their motivation to remain consistently active.

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